

IPBES VA Chapter 4 - Literature review on values considered in decision-making contexts at local level / IPBES values assessment (4.2)

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Project leader

Liliana Bravo Monroy

Data curator(s)

David González-Jiménez (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment highlights the need to assess main findings and lessons learned on valuation methodologies and approaches for decision-making and policymaking at different levels. At the local level, the values underlying formal and informal institutions might provide insights into the pursuit of resilient and sustainable actions. This, this literature review was conducted with two purposes:

- To evaluate the extent to which literature assesses decision-making processes considering if diverse values were included as well as specificities of decision-making contexts at local scales (i.e. application of Decision-Making Typology (DMT) to local contexts) (partially in sub-sections 4.4.1; 4.6.5).
- To analyse inconsistencies, gaps and/or dominant approaches in the historical evolution of values in forestry governance institutions of a place-based case (i.e., the Amazon biome) and their impact on decision making and policy. The Amazon Basin as a region offered a framework to show the role of culture in the way nature is conceptualised, valued, projected through decisions on management and governance, or envisioned in the future (sub-section 4.4.2.1).

This review was carried out following FPIC principles.

Process overview

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Protocol:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** general search without restrictions for relevant publications
- **Search language:** English & Spanish
- **Search engine:** ScienceDirect and Web of Science
- **Search terms:**

Details for the search in ScienceDirect:

TS =
("effectiveness of decision making process protected areas and indigenous communities"; "women as decision makers in community forest management")

Details for the search in Web of Science:

TS =
("effectiveness AND decision-making processes AND protected areas management AND local communities)

Treatment applied: Each article was screened by examining the content of its abstract. Relevant articles were selected.

Given the broad range of subjects focused on institutions, historical perspective and case studies, different databases have been used for performing literature searches to identify potentially relevant publications.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** integration of additional publications through searching in multiple databases.

Details of the searches:

- **Source:** Colombian governmental websites; e.g.:
 - **Types of documents/sources found:** Decrees and regulations. For example:
 - Sistema único de información normativa <http://www.suin-juriscal.gov.co>
 - Parques nacionales naturales de Colombia www.parquesnacionales.gov.co
 - Alcaldía de Bogotá <https://www.alcaldiabogota.gov.co/sisjur/listados/tematica2.jsp?subtema=26256&cadena=c>
 - The ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development www.minambiente.gov.co
 - National Planning Department (DNP) www.dnp.gov.co
 - Ministry of Education www.mineducation.gov.co
 - Instituto Caro y Cuervo <https://lenguasdecolombia.caroycuervo.gov.co/>
 - Ministry of information related to indigenous plans of life <https://siic.mininterior.gov.co/content/planes-de-vida>
- **Source:** Websites of university libraries
 - **Types of documents/sources found:** Books. For example:
 - Domínguez and Gómez 1994
 - Steiner et al. 2014).
- **Source:** Online databases of global institutions such as CBD, Organisation of American States (OAS), FAO, UNEP, UN Sustainable Development, Unesco.
 - **Types of documents/sources found:** Grey literature.

Treatment applied: Each document was screened by examining the content of its introductory paragraphs. Relevant documents were selected.

From both searches, 54 relevant documents were retrieved. The full list can be found in **(A)**.

- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_4.2_2020_(A).pdf

Treatment applied: A set of 30 publications **(B)** were assessed following the procedure and using a predefined list of codes presented in **(R1)**.

- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_4.2_2021_(B).pdf

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.2_2020_(A)	pdf	159 KB	List of 54 relevant publications obtained

				through the literature searches described in this report.
B	IPBES_VA_4.2_2021_(B)	pdf	121 KB	Set of 30 coded publications
R1	IPBES_VA_4.2_2021_(R1)	pdf	214 KB	Procedure and codes used to assess the literature